

Modelling Decarbonization Pathways in the Power Sector in Developing Countries: The case of Argentina

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- Keywords

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Executive Summary

Based on the emission reduction targets established by Argentine Government Authorities, we examined the consistency of these announcements and established energy policy goals up to 2050. Contrasting these targets with a non-restricted optimization model, we found them to be quite similar. Subsequently, a Net Zero scenario was defined, all of which were made using the OSeMOSYS tool.

Several findings emerged, revealing that a Net Zero proposal could bring both advantages and disadvantages. However, further exploration is needed to gain a deeper understanding of replacement energy sources in other sectors of the economy. There are numerous tasks to be addressed in the near future.

1. Introduction

According to Argentina's National Plan of Adaptation and Mitigation to Climate Change and the National Plan of Energy Transition, the Energy Sector accounted for 51% of the total greenhouse gas emissions in 2019. With a commitment to reducing emissions from 366 million tons to 349 million tons by 2030 and achieving neutrality by 2050, the country faces significant challenges in balancing energy needs with environmental objectives.

Given Argentina's reliance on natural gas for energy dispatch, maintaining modern generation technology could provide reliability and help integrate natural gas resources with neighboring countries. However, this approach conflicts with the goal of emission neutrality by 2050.

Guided by the Secretary of Energy of Argentina (SEA) plan, our research focuses on three key questions:

1. Is the SEA plan (BAU scenario) consistent with the optimization made by the OSeMOSYS model?
 2. How does the solution of the unrestricted (Min Cost scenario) model compare to the SEA plan?
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3. How will the Argentinian power mix evolve under a full decarbonization target by 2050 (Net Zero scenario), and what additional investments would be necessary to achieve this goal in the electricity matrix?

2. Methodology

The Starter Data Kit (SDK) for Argentina served as the baseline model, utilizing the corresponding reference energy system (Cannone and Allington, 2021). We updated the installed capacities and historical power generation for the years 2015-2022 to calibrate the model. OSeMOSYS was selected as the modeling framework for the long-term analysis of the energy system. OSeMOSYS, a bottom-up linear programming model, identifies the optimal evolution of the energy-technology mix, ensuring minimum cost, adherence to greenhouse gas emission limits, and satisfaction of all energy demands, among other constraints (Howells et al., 2011).

In light of a recent energy transition report by the Secretary of Energy of Argentina (SEA), our analysis explores alternative approaches. The three scenarios evaluated with OSeMOSYS are:

- The Business-As-Usual scenario with policy (BAU), serving as a baseline scenario that considers the SEA's projected departure and arrival. It aims to transform the electricity generation matrix, currently based on fossil fuel technologies, into a predominantly green matrix.
- The Minimum Cost scenario (MinCost), similar to BAU but without restrictions imposed for 2050. The model seeks to identify the economically most efficient electricity generation technology mix. This scenario aims to assess the deviation of SEA's targets from cost-efficient results.
- The Net Zero scenario, which aims to determine the requirements to meet energy demands without relying on fossil fuel generation by 2050.

Figure 1. Scenario description.

3. Results

Across the three scenarios, we observe a consistent response of the model to the smoothly increasing demand, with power generation increasing accordingly. However, a notable difference arises during the next decade: while the Business-As-Usual (BAU) and Minimum Cost (MinCost) scenarios show more technology substitution than growth, the Net Zero (NZ) scenario exhibits a substantial increase in power generation. This result may be attributed to the electrification of final energy services, highlighting the relevance of adequate energy planning.

Figure 2. Power generation by technology

In the MinCost scenario, we observe a logical increase in power generation from 2030 to 2040. Conversely, in the scenario based on the assumptions of the SEA, there is a decrease in power generation during the same period. This discrepancy may be attributed to a scheme implemented to limit the evolution of certain technologies, aiming to prevent sudden changes in 2050 under the Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario. Notably, an examination of the power capacity in Table 3 reveals a smooth growth trajectory without any generation reversions. Both figures 2 and 3 show a big jump on wind capacity and generation of the NZ scenario. As wind energy has a smaller capacity factor it requires considerably more installed capacity to ensure the same output delivery capacity that could have a Gas Power Plant (CCGT).

Figure 3. Installed Capacity by technology (in GW)

The alignment of SEA targets with the MinCost results suggests efficient planning by the government. However, achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 requires us to consider the Net Zero (NZ) scenario, where fossil fuel technology is phased out. This transition could introduce volatility into the system and may necessitate the development of storage solutions not captured in our current model. Furthermore, it's worth noting that Patagonia offers significant wind potential, indicating the possibility of expanding wind generation. However, challenges persist in high voltage transport capacity, currently a bottleneck in the National Electric System. While our model assumes a proportional increase in transport capacity alongside power generation capacity, real-world implementation may diverge significantly from this assumption.

Figure 4 illustrates the evolution of CO2 emissions, with the BAU and MinCost scenarios displaying similar patterns, while the NZ scenario showcases an efficient pathway to carbon neutrality.

Figure 4. Annual emissions.

Reaching Net Zero (NZ) emissions by 2050 requires a substantial increase in investment, estimated at approximately \$20 billion USD over 20 years. This represents a considerable effort for a developing economy like Argentina, currently undergoing a challenging process of economic transformation. It's important to note that our assumptions include the ability of Argentina to adopt advanced technologies at international costs and achieve similar capital costs to developed countries.

Figure 5. Fixed Capital Costs

We can visualize the total discounted cost of these three scenarios in Figure 6, which illustrates the investment gap of the NZ scenario. The difference reaches its peak at 110 USD billion when compared to the MinCost scenario.

Figure 6. Total Discounted Cost.

4. Discussion

The scenario generation process has not only provided valuable training in simulating diverse energy models but has also built strong capacities in this area. The results indicate that the SEA goals appear reasonable for transitioning to an energy regime. The outcomes from a scenario constrained by the power capacity mixture in 2050 closely resemble those that could have been derived from an optimization process using the OSeMOSYS tool, as reflected in the previous figures.

However, the net-zero (NZ) target set by the Environment Authority is not consistent with the Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario. While the NZ target serves as a theoretical reference, the lack of sufficient base energy dispatch, particularly from efficient Combined Cycle Gas Turbine (CCGT) technologies, may not ensure stability during peak demands. Therefore, future studies should incorporate additional storage mechanisms to address this issue.

Considering Argentina's significant natural gas potential, it's imperative to conduct a thorough analysis of its potential use in transportation compared to electrification. Leveraging the country's substantial Non-Conventional gas potential and existing compressed natural gas (GNV) network, as well as integrating gas interconnections with neighboring countries, could pave the way for an economically sustainable energy system in the southern cone region. Integrating or gasifying transportation may offer more cost-effective alternatives to liquefying gas for export as LNG.

Regarding the investment gap required for NZ development, it poses a significant challenge for a country striving to stabilize its economy and catch up technologically while overcoming capital restrictions. The net present value of the additional investment exceeds 100 billion dollars.

Lastly, adapting the model to accommodate instantaneous adjustments in transport capacity presents a future challenge that requires careful consideration.

5. Conclusion

The use of the OSeMOSYS model has provided valuable insights. Firstly, we observed a contradiction between energy and environmental policies, indicating the need for better coordination between these areas to avoid conflicts in achieving targets.

Secondly, we noted that long-term planning in the Argentinean energy sector demonstrates consistency, as it aligns with goals reached in non-restricted exercises for the power sector.

The transition from fossil fuel technologies to renewables highlights the necessity of expanding power capacity, as evidenced by differences in capacity activity factors. Pursuing a Net Zero target would require greater capital expenditures.

While there are still several tasks to be undertaken to draw solid conclusions, it appears that a Net Zero strategy may present further challenges for Argentina, which need to be carefully evaluated.

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